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EFFECT OF CARBON NANOTUBE CONTENTS ON FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF THERMALLY DEGRADED NANOCOMPOSITE FILMS VIA THE ESSENTIAL WORK OF FRACTURE TEST

M. S. Choi and B. H. Choi, Korea University, Republic of Korea

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Introduction

Fig. Trend of global electric vehicle sales

Fig. A battery pack positioned below (Tesla S)

Fig. Underbody protection (Tesla S)

- A battery pack is located below the vehicle and is protected by underbody shield.
- The shield should be strong enough to protect a battery pack from some sort of obstruction.
- And also it should be light for better fuel efficiency.

Fig. A process from raw material to product

<Objectives of this study>

- We considered thermoplastic material instead of heavy steel.
- Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic with some kinds of nanofillers is one of highly considered materials.
- Final goal is to make underbody shield products and this study is to collect baseline data of low-level materials.

Materials

Matrix	
Polyethylene Terephthalate with Glycol (PETG)	
SK Chem. (PN100)	
Tensile strength (yield)	50 MPa
Elongation (yield)	4.5 %
Density	1270 kg/m ³
Nanofiller	
Multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT, CNT)	
Nanocyl (NC7000)	
Average diameter	9.5 nm
Average length	1.5 μm
Carbon purity	90 %

Fig. Materials information

Barrel temp.	Screw speed	Die temp.	Cooling roll temp.	Cooling roll speed
230°C	20 rpm	225°C	80°C (Top&Middle) 30°C (Bottom)	3.5 m/min

Ø25, L/D ratio 30:1, single screw extruder

Fig. PETG/CNT nanocomposite pellets

Ø48, twin screw extruder

PETG/CNT nanocomposite films

CNT contents 0, 0.5, 1, 2wt%

Thickness 50 μm

Fig. PETG/CNT nanocomposite films

Processing temp.	Extruder speed	Resin pressure	Resin temp.
170-230-215°C (T-Die)	200 rpm	14.2 kgf	232°C

Test Methods

Test Method	Property	Value
Thermal Degradation	Temperature	60 °C
	Time	0, 100, 200, 400 hrs
Fracture Test (EWF test)	Ligament	6, 8, 10, 12 mm
	Strain rate	50 mm/min
	Notch direction	Transverse Direction

Fig. Test conditions

Fig. (a) Drying oven (b) EWF test specimen and apparatus

<EWF test method>

but it was not.

Fig. (a) A load-displacement curve to fracture (b) Determination of EWF parameters – ‘specific work of fracture vs. ligament’ linear regression line

EWF parameters

- The specific essential work of fracture (w_e) [kJ/m²]
 - related to the fracture toughness
 - resistance to crack initiation at a crack tip
- The specific non-essential work of fracture (w_p) [kJ/m³]
 - related to the ductility of polymer films
 - resistance to crack propagation

Results and Discussion

<Thermal degradation>

Fig. SEM images - surfaces of PETG/CNT 2wt% films
(a) 0h (b) 400h thermal degradation

Fig. (a) ATR-FTIR (b) Carboxyl Index curve of PETG films

$$CI = \frac{A_{2700-2400cm^{-1}}}{A_{1520-1490cm^{-1}}} \quad *CI; \text{ Carboxyl Index}$$

<EWF test results>

Fig. 'Ligament vs. Specific work of fracture' linear regression lines of
(a) 0h (b) 100h (c) 200h (d) 400h

Results and Discussion

Slope (βw_p)	0h	100h	200h	400h
neat PETG	1.000	0.904	0.935	1.113
PETG/CNT 0.5wt%	0.952	0.720	0.763	0.735
PETG/CNT 1wt%	0.933	0.474	0.765	0.557
PETG/CNT 2wt%	0.714	0.537	0.305	0.228

Intercept (w_e)	0h	100h	200h	400h
neat PETG	1.000	1.185	1.132	0.853
PETG/CNT 0.5wt%	0.309	0.682	0.650	0.653
PETG/CNT 1wt%	0.490	1.203	0.758	1.177
PETG/CNT 2wt%	0.751	0.817	1.205	1.301

Fig. Comparisons of EWF parameters

*normalized by the value of neat PETG_0h

Results and Discussion

Fig. SEM images of fracture surfaces

Conclusion

- PETG/CNT nanocomposite films with various kinds of CNT contents were studied.
- They were thermally degraded by heat and qualified by ATR-FTIR.
- Fracture properties were studied by EWF test method.
- It is natural that CNTs make films weaker to crack propagation.
- We expected that CNTs make nanocomposite films have stronger resistance to crack initiation (fracture toughness)
- It is expected that there was a problem about a CNT distribution.

<Future work>

- We need to figure out why nanocomposite films have poorer fracture properties and find the solution.
- We will product carbon fiber reinforced nanocomposite sheets and need to check their mechanical, fractural and other kinds of properties.

The logo of Korea University is a circular seal. It features a central shield with a figure, surrounded by the Latin motto "LIBERTAS JUSTITIA VERITAS" in an arc. The text "KOREA UNIVERSITY" and the year "1905" are also visible within the seal.

Thank you for your attention!

choims9179@korea.ac.kr